

PART-TIME WORK AND ACADEMIC SUCCESS A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS EXPERIENCES AT BUIITEMS IN THE FACULTY SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (FSSH)

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Abstract

A part-time job is a form of employment that carries few hours per week than a full-time job. This research is carried out to check the part time job effects on the students academic achievements of Social sciences and humanities in BUIITEMS Quetta. The data was collected from the students of FSSH using Qualitative Research in which the total number of population was 219 students. Education, sociology, IR, English, and fine arts departments of BUIITEMS were selected as the sample of the study. Based on preliminary research, students' academic performance can be impacted by part-time employment in both favourable and unfavourable ways. According to the research, students who work part-time frequently struggle with time management issues, higher stress levels, and less time for studying. However, some students also mention positive outcomes like increased financial security and experiences. The study shows that part-time jobs had a positive effect on student's GPAs since they had greater GPAs than 3. The study outcomes expand our understanding of how undergraduate students need to maintain an appropriate balance between part-time jobs and academic obligations in order to help students successfully balance their academic and employment responsibilities, the study seeks to offer insightful information by examining this problem within the context of Faculty of societies and humanities BUIITEMS Quetta. This information may then be used to inform university policies and support system. In the end, the study wants to provide students with all the information that require to determine a part-time job while pursuing their studies.

Introduction

For university students, part-time employment implies scheduling less than full-time hours. Employees are typically regarded as part-time if they regularly work fewer than 30 hours per week. It typically refers to working fewer days or hours per workweek. Academic performance, which is determined by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average, is the degree to which a student, instructor, or institution has

met their short- or long-term educational goals. The impact of working students' academic performance in BUIITEMS QUETTA is the main topic of this study. The research primarily focuses on working students at BUIITEMS. Buitems students have a part-time job since there are so many costs. Several students who work part-time jobs miss out on their extracurricular activities. In addition to the stress brought on by emotional and physical tiredness, students are also in danger

of dropping out, having delayed graduation rates, having little time to study, eating poorly, and having attendance problems. Balochistan has an extremely small number of universities, giving students very few options for finishing their degrees. Due to the economic crisis, independence, rejection of students to accept educational scholarships and population level of students, this study will examine Balochistan's working students.

Consequently, this study aims to examine how students who work see how their studies are affected by their employment. I do not observe any negative effects of a marginal increase in work hours on student grades in the sample. The fact that pupils have been spending less time studying recently may be one factor in this. 2011's Babcock and Darks.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

There are varieties of economic backgrounds among students. Their financial support comes from their parents. In the meanwhile, many students shoulder their costs and work part-time jobs to lessen their financial problems, which have an impact on their academic performance. They are worn out and unbalanced both physically and psychologically.

The increasing trend of students taking up part-time jobs while pursuing their studies has raised concerns about its potential impact on their academic performance. There is a need to examine the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic performance, particularly in terms of their grades, attendance, and overall engagement in their studies. This study aims to investigate whether the demands of part-time jobs and the time devoted to them may negatively affect students' academic performance, and to what extent. It also seeks to explore how students manage their time and cope with the added responsibilities of both working and studying. The findings of this study will be useful in developing strategies to support students who work part-time to strike a balance between their work and studies, as well as in guiding policymakers and educators in addressing the

potential impact of part-time jobs on students' academic performance.

1.2 Research Objective

Objective:

- To find out the problems of the students carrying out part-time jobs.
- To find out the academic challenges faced by students who work part-time

1.3 Research Question

- What problems do students face in managing part time jobs and academic responsibilities?
- What are the academic challenges experienced by students who engage in part time job?

1.5 Limitations of Study

The study's findings may only apply to BUITEMS University and cannot be generalized to other universities due to unique factors such as location, student demographics, and institutional practices that can influence the impact of part-time jobs on academic performance.

1.6 Delimitations of the study

- The sample size could be determined based on practical considerations such as time, resources, and availability of participants.
- The study may have a specific timeframe within which data is collected, such as a particular academic year or semester.

THEORATICAT FRAMEWORK

Astin's Student Involvement Theory & Part-Time Jobs

Astin argued that a student's academic success is strongly influenced by the degree of their involvement in educationally purposeful activities (e.g., studying, attending lectures, joining discussions, group work). moderate part-time work may enhance involvement indirectly:

- Students may become more disciplined and organized.
- Financial relief from a job may reduce stress, allowing better academic focus.

Skills like teamwork, communication, and responsibility gained at work may carry over into academic task.

Literature Review

This study focuses that Part-time jobs are a common aspect of student life, with many students working to support their studies or cover living expenses. However, the impact of part-time jobs on academic performance remains a topic of debate among researchers. While some studies suggest that working part-time can enhance students' time management skills and provide valuable work experience, others suggest that it can lead to increased stress and reduced academic achievement. Students who work part-time may struggle with managing their time effectively, which can lead to a lack of focus on their academic responsibilities. They may find it difficult to balance their work hours with their study time, resulting in a decrease in their academic performance. Students who work part-time may also have less time and energy to participate in extracurricular activities or attend academic events. This can impact their overall engagement in their academic life, which can negatively impact their grades.

In this literature review, we aim to explore the relationship between part-time jobs and students' academic performance by examining the existing literature on this topic." A study by Kuo, Chen, and Lu (2015) found that students who worked more than 20 hours per week had lower academic performance compared to those who worked less or did not work at all. The study also found that students who worked in jobs related to their field of study had better academic performance. It is generally accepted that student employment can boost or assist in the development of specific human qualities, such as responsibility, work organization, and time management, which may in turn improve academic performance. Even though most on-the-job training mostly enhances non-cognitive abilities, which cannot be assessed by traditional school tests. The majority of nursing students said this helped them develop their confidence and skills. Employment limits

the amount of time available for educational activities, which might have a negative impact on academic performance. Work may affect a student's dedication to and attitude toward learning. Also, it was discovered that students who work primarily for financial gain have lower marks than those who labor to develop career-specific abilities, but higher grades than those driven by a desire for broad job experience. Student employment, in the opinion of faculty, administrators, and staff who counsel students on effective time management, shows a lack of dedication to obtaining a degree. Another study by Bynner and Parsons (2002) found that students who worked long hours during term time had lower grades than those who did not work or worked fewer hours. However, the study also found that working during vacations did not have a significant impact on academic performance.

It is also noted that time management for students becomes challenging because they occasionally lack time management skills. They spend more time working than studying, which undoubtedly affects their academic performance in comparison to students who do not work and receive high grades and have high CGPAs. On the other hand, it has been noticed that students have a more free time during breaks and are only able to manage their jobs, which has no bearing on academic achievement. A study by Mortimer, Staff, Oesterle, and Lerner (2011) found that students who worked in jobs that provided opportunities for skill development, such as internships, had higher academic performance compared to those who worked in jobs that did not provide such opportunities. Working part-time can have an impact on a student's academic performance, but it can also present several chances at the same time. As is widely known, for any job or profession in life, there are perks and drawbacks. Students who are limited to their studies only have less experience and knowledge about the world than those who work around and have an interest in other fields as well. Companies that offer internship facilities are proven to be good for the better future of

students because it not only provides the opportunity to explore but also can boost their confidence and they experience many useful things as well.

Part-time and occasional full-time employment for students is becoming a more widespread practice globally. Working while in school gives kids a natural indicator of the standards they'll need to meet to perform well in their future careers. Further research has recently revealed that students who work part-time can readily build teamwork, customer service, communication, and skills. Students have the opportunity to directly relate their part-time employment experiences to improve and hone their academic motivation, knowledge, and employment chances. Part-time employment, especially in the higher education industry, is frequently seen from the perspective of students as an introduction to the real world that will help with both their personal and professional growth. The performance of students is frequently impacted by part-time employment. Despite its benefits, part-time employment frequently necessitates fewer study hours. So, the purpose of this study is to investigate how part-time employment affects students' academic performance.

A meta-analysis by Ginther and Pollak (2004) found that the negative impact of working on academic performance was stronger for students from low-income families compared to those from high-income families. When compared to students from wealthy households, individuals who support their families live more burdensome lives since they have a greater number of problems to deal with at home and have to work more to manage their finances. They also have more goals and aspirations in life to achieve. Students from low-income families have many issues to deal with and find it way more difficult to manage their family issues and manage their income. They have to work harder and have many goals and many aims in life to fulfill. These circumstances have a significant impact on their study, as they occasionally don't have enough

time to study. They are always stressed and depressed.

Young people from less wealthy homes put in additional hours at work out of necessity and hardship to pay for a university education. Most frequently expressed was the desire to make money. The second reason was a desire for independence. Many students have set financial independence as a goal, but from a student's point of view, it could also mean increasing personal autonomy and benefiting from time spent outside the customary boundaries of home and school. A study by Zagorsky (2005) found that the negative impact of working on academic performance was stronger for students in their first year of college compared to those in later years. It is also noted that first-year students at any institution find themselves very overburdened as compared to other years. The main reason for this load is that they lack experience, which makes it difficult for them to manage their studies and jobs. Additionally, they don't manage their time well, choosing to prioritize one over the other, which has a significant negative impact on their future.

They occasionally second-guess their choices and believe they were worthless, which can cause despair and make them failures in life. The physical and emotional health of students can indeed suffer from the combination of full-time schooling and part-time employment, as several studies have revealed. It might have a bad effect on a student's academic achievement. Students who work part-time are likely to miss lectures and feel that they could have gotten better scores if they hadn't been working because there are so many lessons to make up for.

A study by Green, Henley, and Sturgeon (2003) found that working more than 15 hours per week had a negative impact on academic performance. Every person, whether a student or not, has a set amount of time they can work before they become too exhausted and stressed to complete any more work. Additionally, research has shown that people cannot work for more than a certain amount of time before becoming too mentally fatigued and stressed to complete any more

productive tasks. Since the brain only functions up to a certain point or limit before becoming overloaded, this is also true for students who attempt to balance work and study while doing more work. Another study by Kim and Kim (2010) found that part-time work had a negative effect on the academic performance of high school students, but only if the student worked more than 20 hours per week. Working part-time usually have adverse effect on studies and extracurricular activities of students. Usually schools, colleges and universities run yearly students who work part-time unable to give enough time to study and revise for academic exams and assignments. A study by Watanabe (2008) found that working part-time had a positive effect on the studies and performance of Japanese university students, but only if the students worked less than 20 hours per week. A study by Hsin and Fung (2008) found that working part-time had a negative effect on the academic performance of Taiwanese high school students, but only if the student worked more than 20 hours per week. The authors suggested that this may be due to the reduced time and energy for academic activities and the increased stress associated with balancing work and school.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is a systematic approach used to conduct research, encompassing all the activities that are involved in the process of conducting research. This includes selecting the research topic, formulating research questions, designing the study, collecting data through various methods such as surveys or interviews, analysing the data using appropriate statistical methods, and interpreting the findings.

Research Design and Approach

The research approach for this study will be qualitative and the design will be phenomenological. A type of research that explains the nature of themes through the way people experience them by German philosopher Edmund Husserl (1859- 1938).

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of this study will be 216 students of BUIITEMS University who were engaged in part-time jobs related to their practical involvement. This research population includes students aged 18 to 24 years. Both male and female students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds were included in the research population. "The research population comprises students pursuing degrees in BUIITEMS. Only students who were engaged in part-time jobs related to their practical involvement. Due to resource constraints, the study was limited to students who are part of BUIITEMS.

3.4 Sample Size of the Study

The sample size in the current study will consist of 12 undergraduate students who were engaged in part-time jobs. For the phenomenological approach, the sample size would be six to fifteen.

Conclusion

Part-time employment affects the students' academic performance, and it depends on the nature of the job and the duration of the employment. The study discovered the impact of part-time jobs on academic performance among students of FSSH at BUIITEMS QUETTA. Several key findings have developed through the analysis of different studies, surveys, and data collection. In this research, it was declared that part-time employment impacts the academic performance of students in a negative and positive form. In these inquiries, numerous pros and cons of part-time work was realized that have an impact on students' academic outcomes. On the positive side, part-time employment can assist students in building critical skills like independence, accountability, and time management. Additionally, it might enhance their capacity for prioritizing commitments and multitasking. A notable quantity of students at BUIITEMS are engaged in part-time jobs. These jobs provide them with financial support, professional experience, and the opportunity to create basic skills. It was observed that balancing the demands of work and academics can be

challenging for students, potentially affecting their academic performance.

Moreover, the research shows that the impact of part-time jobs on academic performance is not maintained and can change depending on various factors. Factors such as the number of hours worked, job responsibilities, and the level of support from employers and academic institutions can significantly influence the outcome. Students who work fewer hours, have flexible work schedules and receive support from their employers and academic institutions tend to fare better academically.

Recommendations:

- Researchers should provide valuable insights into the relationship between part-time jobs and academic performance. It aims to identify the potential benefits and challenges faced by students working part-time along with strategies to effectively manage their academic responsibilities.
- Future researchers, educators, teachers, and Policymakers should serve as foundation for part-time job holders to make informed decisions about balancing work and academics effectively.
- Universities should award scholarships to students who are unable to pay their tuition fees.

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